

had been mixed with fertilizer N during soil incorporation was retained as seed for further multiplication. In monocrop and intercrop plots, fresh azolla was inoculated. Adverse effects of more than 50 kg N/ha would be reduced by minimizing mixing of fertilizer N and azolla or by seeding fresh azolla for further multiplication.

The poor response of azolla to applied P may be due to the high available P in the soil and its increased availability under flooded conditions.

Monocropping for 20 d and dual cropping for 50 d resulted in higher yields of fresh azolla, contributing more N/day, dry matter content, and K

Table 2. Effect of N and cultivation method interaction on yield of fresh azolla, Bangalore, India, 1983 wet season.

N (kg/ha)	Total yield of fresh azolla (t/ha)			
	Monocropping	Intercropping	Dual cropping	Mean
0	21.0	16.0	37.8	24.9
50	19.8	15.4	37.1	24.1
100	18.5	15.6	31.5	21.8
Mean	19.8	15.6	35.4	23.6
LSD (P=0.05)	2.4 ^a	3.0 ^b		

^aBetween 2 methods of cultivation at same level of N. ^bBetween 2 N levels in same cultivation method.

content of dry matter. Monocrop azolla did not experience any competition with rice. Intercrop azolla suffered

considerable competition with rice for all growth factors, in particular light and nutrients. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of seedling age and leaf removal on rice grain and straw yields

N. R. Das and N. Mukherjee, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, Nadia, West Bengal, India

We studied the effect of age of seedling and removal of leaf on rice grain and straw yields during kharif 1988, at the Seed Farm (23.5° N, 89.0° E, and 9.75 mean sea level). Treatments were three seedling ages and four leaf removal levels, in a split-plot design with four replications.

Soil was clayey loam (0.61% organic C, 0.59% total N, 14 kg available P/ha, 208 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8). Fertilizer was 40-50-50 kg NPK/ha

applied at plowing and 50 kg N/ha applied 30 d after transplanting (DT). IR8 seedlings at 21, 28, and 35 d after seeding were transplanted 20 Jul at 25-×

15-cm spacing, four seedlings/hill. Leaves were removed (0, 25, 50, and 100%) 1 mo after transplanting in 7.5-× 2.0-m subplots.

Seedling age did not significantly affect grain and straw yields. Grain and straw yields decreased with increased leaf removal (see table). □

Effect of seedling age and leaf removal on rice grain and straw yields of IR8. West Bengal, India, 1988.

Seedling age (d)	Yield (t/ha)									
	No leaves removed		25% of leaves removed		50% of leaves removed		100% of leaves removed		Mean	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
21	4.8	5.0	3.6	4.0	3.6	4.0	2.8	3.6	3.7	4.1
28	4.4	4.7	4.4	5.0	4.0	4.5	3.8	4.7	4.2	4.7
35	4.5	4.9	3.7	4.2	3.2	3.5	3.1	3.3	3.6	4.0
Mean	4.6	4.8	3.9	4.4	3.6	4.0	3.2	3.9	—	—
LSD (0.05)	Leaf removal		0.7	grain						
			0.7	straw						

Influence of potassium and kinetin on protein partitioning in rice

I. Sakeena and M. A. Salam, Kerala Agricultural University (KAU), Cropping Systems Research Centre (CSRC), Karamana 695002, Trivandrum, India

We examined protein partitioning in rice, using short-duration Triveni in a summer 1987 field experiment at Karamana (8.5° N, 77.9° E, and 29 m above sea level). Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam, pH 4.5, with 84.3, 13.6, 63.8 ppm available NPK.

Treatments, a factorial combination of four potassium levels (0, 14.5, 29.1, 58.1) and four kinetin spray treatments, are given in Table 1. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

K as KCl was applied 50% basal and 50% at panicle initiation; 70 kg N and